

STUDY OF PHRASEOLOGY ISSUES IN WORLD LINGUISTICS AND TRANSLATION STUDIES

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Annotation The word "phraseology" is derived from the Greek word "phrasis," which means a device of speech. The word has two meanings. The first is a term used to describe a fixed layer of linguistics, that is, a particular layer that studies phraseological units, and the second is a term that serves to describe a set of phraseological units. The term phraseological unit was first introduced into linguistics by V.V.Vinogradov. Along with the terms phraseological unit and phraseology, the terms idiom and idiomatics are also used.

Key words: *specific lexicology, general lexicology, sister languages, lexical meaning, phraseological combination, graduality and stability;*

The objects of study of phraseology are PhUs, ie fixed phrases, expressions, all phraseological units in speech. The lexical-semantic level includes two large sections of language that are inextricably linked. These are lexicology (Greek *lexikos* - word and *logos* - study) and semiotics. According to the material studied, lexicology is divided into two types: specific lexicology, ie lexicology of a language and general lexicology.

General lexicology covers all language problems and focuses on different language materials. In addition to general and specific lexicology, there are comparative and comparative (contrastive) lexicology. Comparative lexicology primarily studies the similarities of sister languages, while comparative lexicology studies the similarities and similarities not only of sister languages but also of non-sister languages..

The subject of semiotics covers a wide range of issues related to the lexical meaning of the word. The term "semiotics" is derived from the Greek words "semacia - meaning" and "logos - study". In some cases, greek word "semiano" means "to express". The term "semasiology" is also used as a synonym for the term "semantics". Just as words cannot exist without meaning, so lexicology and semantics cannot exist without each other. Lexicology is the study of the entire vocabulary of a language. It identifies historical changes in the structure of the lexicon, a variety of words from

other languages, archaisms, neologisms, literary lexicon, slang, regional, dialectal terminology, specialization and other lexically divided words based on clear principles considers different lexical categories and types.

As the name implies, it explores two different natures of the system. First, lexical semantics differs from grammatical semantics in the semantic boundaries of language. Second, with the help of this system, word semantics can be divided as a lexical element. The language system, dictionary structure and lexical-semantic systems play an important role in distinguishing the set of nominative devices that make up the lexical system from the vocabulary. They represent the result of a complex interrelationship between a word and its meanings, and the generalization of these results. This interaction takes place in two areas of language, namely, nominative-classification and lexical integration. Therefore, lexical-semantic categories can be of two types. The first is a lexical-semantic group of polysemous words, expressed in the form of semantic variants in the language. Each has its own meaning (like lexemes). The units in which lexemes occur in speech are also called word usage and lexemes. Here, a lex is a term that is formed by analogy based on the characteristics of the units of speech (such as morph (morpheme) and background (phoneme)). The contrast between a word as a unit of language and a unit of speech can also be given by other terms, such as a word-lexeme and a word-part.

A.I. Smirnisky calls them lexical-semantic variants.¹ In other words, we pay attention to the actual (speech) significance of the word in the process of using it in each act. G. Paul terminologically differentiated the whole meaning and meaning of a word in the individual acts in which they participate, i.e., he calls the former a usual and the latter an occasional meaning.

In linguistics, the term phraseology was used by Charles Bally, stylistics combined with science, but the idea of recognizing phraseology as a science famous linguist scientist prof. It is E. F. Polivanov. Slave to this idea another of the scientists who supported him is the famous linguist V. V. Vinogradov. She is in a number of his scientific studies, he taught phraseological combinations in the Russian language collects and semantically divides them into groups. E.D. Polivanov and

Thoughts on phraseology raised by V. V. Vinogradov later, it prompted the emergence of many studies in this field. But until now, there are opinions about whether or not to consider phraseology as a science did not fully find the solution. Idiom

phraseologisms, phraseological combinations and between static phrases (proverbs and proverbs, other phraseology equivalent to a sentence).

According to several differences, some scholars divide phraseology into 2 types: narrow and broad they interpret it in the sense. When it is understood in a broad sense (L.P. Smith, V.P. Zhukov, V.N. Teliya, N.M. Shansky) proverbs and sayings in phraseology, folk colloquial phrases belonging to his work, a number of forms of speech (greeting, sayings of farewell) are also included. But phraseology is widely used. It is no exaggeration to say that the problem of understanding has not been solved yet it won't happen.

Development of phraseology as a special field of linguistics experienced difficult roads. Even the famous English linguist Smirnitsky also supported the fact that phraseology is a separate field of linguistics. It was a branch of lexicology with the theory of phraseological combinations despite the study of phraseology, it is necessary to study the syntactic part of the language. If we do not recognize phraseology as a separate field, then as a separate science Smirnitsky said in his work "Lexikologia angliškovo yazyka" that we cannot say.

Until the 50s of the last century, phraseology was still part of Uzbek linguistics was not formed as an independent field. It is about phraseology in this period preliminary information, the first theoretical ideas about stable compounds, grammar and to stylistics, to the study of the artistic skills of some Uzbek poets and writers can be seen in dedicated works. Such works A. Gulomov, U. Tursunov, A famous linguist and literary critic like V. Abdullayev, H. Zarif, N. Mallayev belongs to the pen of scientists. All modern linguists word, considered one of the most basic units of language, however, that it was the nature of his character. As for the subject and the sound of the word based on the terms set a clear awareness of the subject property of the initial basis.

The appearance of specific sounds (sound of the word), and relations between the event being. If this were not so, all the items and events in a variety of languages are different, but the same would be called. The main functional and structural language and highlevel asymmetric unit. Its semantic, morphological structure and complex semantic content of these words, grammatical features characteristic for specific groups of lexical meanings strictly differentiated. It is a hallmark of the group, the semantics of the word.

For example, the semantics of the word and the corresponding part of the semantic individual words. In many languages, the meaning of a word or words of similar schemes and a series of lexical and grammatical types may find their form. Phraseology is an intermediary field, being close, in the reference literature, both to vocabulary studies, since it studies fixed word combinations, characterized by a unitary meaning, as well as to syntax, since phraseologic phenomena are defined by syntactic relations of various kinds, which are realized on a syntagmatic axis. Given the expressive nature of phraseologic phenomena, these have also been associated to stylistics. Taking into consideration the possibility of differentiating styles and functional variants of a language by analysing phraseologic units, it has been particularly drawn closer to functional stylistics.

But beyond the closeness to different linguistic disciplines, phraseology tends to be regarded as an autonomous discipline, with its own object and methods of investigation. The term phraseology designates the discipline as well as its object, the set or totality of phraseologic units in a given language. According to the origin of phraseologisms, a line has been drawn between two areas of investigation, namely, linguistic phraseology understood as a community's means of expression and literary phraseology including aphorisms, witticism, word combinations with an accidental character, belonging to certain writers, outstanding people. As an autonomous discipline, the object of research of phraseology consists in phraseologic units from a given language (or a group of languages).

We believe a rigorous definition of co-occurrence phenomena in general, and phraseology in particular, needs to take a stand regarding at least the following six parameters.

- the nature of the elements involved in a phraseologism;
- the number of elements involved in a phraseologism;
- the number of times an expression must be observed before it counts as a phraseologism;
- the permissible distance between the elements involved in a phraseologism;
- the degree of lexical and syntactic flexibility of the elements involved;
- the role that semantic unity and semantic non-compositionality / non-predictability play in the definition.

As to the first criterion, the definition of a phraseologism we will adopt is among the broadest conceivable ones. We consider a phraseologism to be the co-occurrence of a

form or a lemma of a lexical item and any other kind of linguistic element, which can be, for example, another (form of a) lexical item; a grammatical pattern (as opposed to, say, a grammatical relation), i.e. when a particular lexical item tends to occur in / co-occur with a particular grammatical construction (the fact that the verb is mostly used in the passive is a frequently cited case in point).

We maintain a very productive idea flashed out by the linguist and consisting in that phraseological meaning cannot be realized without the existence of definite structures, i.e. it is impossible to study the features of phraseological units without knowledge of their structure. There are, as far as its scheme goes, seven main structural types of phraseological units in the English language. They are as follows
A.I. Smirnitsky "Лексикология английского языка". Monograph M., 1956.

1. Unitop phraseological units (the term was introduced by A.I. Smirnitsky consisting of one notional and one functional lexeme, or one notional and two or three functional lexemes. By functional lexemes one should consider lexemes which do not function as independent members of the sentence and serve for word connection in the sentence (prepositions, conjunctions), and also for characterization of the categories of number, definiteness or indefiniteness of nouns (or articles).

2. Phraseological units with the structure of subordinate or coordinate combination of words (to have a finger in every pie „to be involved in every plan; high and mighty” the powerful minority).

3. Phraseological units with the partially predicative structure (i.e. lexeme + subordinate clause): ships that pass in the night momentary encounters).

4. Phraseological units with the structure of subordinate clause (when pigs fly (colloq.) never);

5. Phraseological units of nominative-communicative class, i.e. verbal constructions with the structure of a word combination with a verb in the form of infinitive and the structure of a sentence with a verb in the passive voice (break the ice “C to make a beginning > the ice is broken the beginning is made).

6. Phraseological units with the structure of a simple or complex sentence (A bird in the hand is worth two in the bush. Better an egg today than a hen tomorrow; Do you see any green in my eye? Do you really think me to be so naive? Tell it to the marines! Nonsense!).

7. Phraseological units that are equivalents of a sentence, i.e. some structural types of interjectional constructions that have a power of expression and are characterized by independent (its own) intonation (by George! – Upon my word!; my foot! – I’m far

from believing it!). However, referring of interjections of this type to sentence equivalents is not undisputable .

In the literature dealing with phraseology, different terms, such as idiom, phraseme or word-group have often been used to refer to the same category. Each of them is defined according to different criteria and, for this reason, each term leads to broader or narrower definitions and views.

Nevertheless, despite the heterogeneity of terminology, there seems to be a general agreement in that a phraseological unit is a fixed word-combination whose main features are summarized in Corpas Pastor's Manual de fraseología. Here, she lists the main features of a phraseological unit, summarizing them from previous different authors. According to Corpas Pastor a phraseological unit : is an expression made of various words; is institutionalized (institutionalization); presents some kind of semantic or syntactic specificity (idiomaticity); has different degrees of stability (graduality and stability); is possible a certain variation of its components (variation); is usually characterized by an high frequency of use.

In general function is a role which an element plays in activity of that structure, part of which it makes. Some functions are constant, i.e. inherent in all phraseological units in any conditions of their realization, other functions are variable, peculiar only to some classes of phraseological units. Communicative, cognitive and nominative functions refer to the constant functions.

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